

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KIBREAB****FIRST NAME: FITSUM****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US spelling

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used MSWord 2010 on Windows 8

THE ESSENTIALS OF GOOD ACADEMIC WRITING**1) INTRODUCTION**

Learning academic writing is the most essential and at the forefront of the step of any academia and professional. It helps to communicate with your audience in the best way possible using more structured, well punctuated, and easy to understand, and grammatically correct writing to convey the message. The coursepack which is provided for the first period, as a study material, included some of these basic elements of academic writing. Reading the coursepack and watching the video gave me much information, where some of them helped me to refresh my knowledge, and some of them were new as well. This course material is very appreciative and informative and it includes so many essential topics including but not limited to essay writing, styles, referencing, Chicago style, Latin abbreviations and expressions and so forth. The video had also some good information presented in a summarized way including, format the response paper, saving the response paper, using the US (United States) or UK (United Kingdom) spelling, quotations and citations. I have discussed some of these elements I have learned from these two course materials below.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Essay writing is the fundamental tool of each and every course (program). The doctoral degree program (commonly called PhD) course provided in EUCLID is unique in that it engages the student with full of writing response papers, major papers as well as creating questions (quiz). Hence, understanding the basics of essay writing is an indispensable and required skill to provide those response papers with the level of expectation at graduate level. The elements covered in the essay writing mechanics were:

starting the essay, researching the topic, organizing your idea, writing the essay, referencing the essay, and submitting the essay.

The course pack has discussed in detail about the importance of a persuasive essay. An academic essay should be strong enough that has the capability of convincing the reader based on evidence (EUCLID 2015, 2). This point is imperative because if the reader is not convinced with what is reading she or he would be put off or may not read it with focus and concentration as a result the intended outcome of the essay may not be achieved. The main point in essay writing is the provision of a strong thesis statement and an argument and this should be supported with evidence from credible resources (EUCLID 2015, 2). However, to get credible resources is not an easy task as it seems at first. Not all writing documents should be considered as sources of evidence for your essay; so we need to critically analyze the information on these sources (EUCLID 2015, 2). While presenting the evidence we should include all information whether they support the proposed thesis statement or oppose it (EUCLID 2015, 3). To do we need to have an initial plan at the very beginning of the essay writing so that it would help how to answer the question of the topic, which information you will you use and how to structure the essay (EUCLID 2015, 2).

The other point that attracted me in the course pack is that writing an essay is not a simple job and you should have to read more a head of it. Writing essay needs plenty of time on searching, reading, thinking, and writing (EUCLID 2015, 2). I also found it fascinating the topic about note taking. At this level just reading is not adequate we need to take note and it is clearly stated when we should take notes and how do we take notes. It is also made clear that during note taking we should write the bibliographic details of everything we read. This course pack also advised not to procrastinate tasks since this could cause unnecessary delay and the consequence would be serious academic penalties. To avoid such problem it is a good idea to start early so that you have enough time do all the basics such as editing and revising the papers (EUCLID 2015, 2).

The other important step of essay writing communicated in the coursepack is organizing your idea. After making extensive search of your topic you need to organize your idea and you could make a plan again (EUCLID 2015, 3). The other point that impressed me was that essay writing needs both critical thinking and creative thinking (EUCLID 2015, 3). Essay structuring also discussed in detail in the pack and an essay should include Introduction, Body, and Conclusion (EUCLID 2015, 4). This is a crucial step in essay writing, as the way an essay is structured would have a significant impact on the readers' perception. Here, I found it interesting to learn that the introduction starts with general idea and go to the specific point whereas the conclusion goes from specific to general (EUCLID 2015, 4). I was not aware about this before, however, I would use this concept in my future essays. The way we write the paragraphs of the body part was one of the important points clarified in this study material. All paragraphs should have a topic sentence and then followed with supporting sentences that clarify it (EUCLID 2015, 4). The first time I came across this topic sentence was during my undergraduate study in the "English for sophomore students." Though I have some idea about this it is good to refresh my mind on this issue. It was also mentioned that the conclusion part is a round off the sum up and new information or new ideas should not be presented (EUCLID

2015, 4). This reminds me the course I took during my postgraduate study entitled “Writing and Reviewing an Epidemiological Papers Module” where I learned how to write the conclusion and what should be written in this section.

3) WHAT IS AN EXCELLENT PAPER-STYLE

This section discussed about an excellent paper and style; a style includes but not limited to saving the paper, using US or UK spelling, plagiarism, citation, footnotes, referencing and so forth. On page seven the coursepack informed us on how to save the paper properly (i.e including canonical name- first and last name, course code, and period code). At the same page it recommended us to use either the US or the UK spelling consistently throughout the paper. This point was very strange for me since I was not aware that there is a UK/US English in the MS office. I used to write my document and just correcting my spelling just when I see a red line for my written words. But now I am aware that I have to select the document after I write my paper and apply the spelling check using either of them thanks to this course pack and the video study material provided in Vimeo for this period. I also found it fascinating about the punctuation mark and the quotations mark introduced on page seven. I have used the quotation and punctuation marks in my postgraduate study, but I did not know that there was a difference in the position of the period (full stop) with the US and UK system.

Using information from different sources to transfer information or to provide support for your thesis statement or problem statement is part of the learning process. However, to use ideas or information from other sources without giving credit or recognition to the author is considered as plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 9). The other good point I have never thought about it was that if someone writes a paper and I submit it to my instructor as if I write it myself without giving credit to this person, this would be considered as plagiarism as well (EUCLID 2015, 9). It was also discussed regarding the reason why it is good to mention the sources: plagiarism is wrong and unethical, not fair to take someone’s work without credit and it is serious academic offence (EUCLID 2015, 9).

This coursepack also discussed about citation. According to this coursepack there are two ways of citation: in text-citation and list of works cited (15). The in text-citation was given with the name of the author and page number (16). I wondered why the year was not included in the citation because this was different from what I learned in my previous studies. The coursepack also mentioned on page twenty what long quotations mean and also mentioned that four or more lines could be considered long quotations as a rule of thumb. I learned new thing about when not to cite a source of information on page thirty. Here it is stated that if the information is a common knowledge where a common knowledge is defined as either a known idea or information or an idea mentioned in different sources, it is not required to be cited (EUCLID 2015, 30). I was also learned about list of works cited, and the bibliography/referencing format for books, online books, websites, and footnote referencing (EUCLID 2015, 33-36).

4) CHICAGO STYLE AND USAGE

The Chicago style where sometimes referred as “Turabian Style” is the style of formatting all kinds of research papers and books. This topic has discussed about many things including abbreviations & acronyms, capitalization, compound words, emphasis: italics/quotes, numbers & dates, and quotations. On page 66 it is discussed about the abbreviations. The Chicago style recommended not to use a lower-case abbreviation to begin a sentence and it also explained not to start a sentence with acronym unless there is a good reason to do so or not to spell it out (EUCLID 2015, 66). It was also discussed about scholarly abbreviations and recommended that they are only used in parentheses not outside of it (EUCLID 2015, 66). I have never thought of the position of these abbreviations even I remember sometimes I have used them outside of the parentheses. Regarding acronyms, the first they are introduced should be spell out with the acronyms in parentheses or their source phrase in parentheses thereafter they can be used (EUCLID 2015, 66). On this same page I found one interesting point which I never noticed before was that the plural form of the acronym does not take apostrophe we just add a lower case s.

This course pack has also discussed regarding capitalization. Capitalization refers to the style we use to write the words using uppercase and lowercases and it has three forms (i.e., full caps, heading caps, and sentence caps) (EUCLID 2015, 67). I have used the full caps and sentence caps in my previous writings whereas the heading caps form is new for me. Particularly I never practiced that capitalizing the first and last words. Moreover, the prepositions like between and against I used to capitalize the first letter but for the other forms like in, of, at as well as the articles I have been writing them in lower case. Nevertheless, I have now learned how to use this style and hopefully I will use this properly in my future essay writings.

5) CONCLUSION

The topics covered in this coursepack for this period are very important including, essay writing, styles, plagiarism, referencing, the Chicago style, citation, the Latin words, and so on. These basic elements are essentials of good academic writing and I am very optimistic that by the end of this course I will be in a better position on writing my papers. The knowledge I have gained from the coursepack so far are amazing. Now I know how to edit my paper either using the US English or the UK English and I am also aware that I have to use this style throughout my paper consistently. I have also learned that how to develop the essay writing, how to organize it, how to write the first draft and editing. As the DIPH course is, like other courses, needs writing several response papers and major papers I will have to write at the end of every period with the level of expectation of writing skill. And this coursepack has taught me the basics of it and I really appreciate EUCLID for choosing this kind of teaching method.

REFERENCES

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